

MEDICATIONAL CORRECTION FOR MORPHOLOGICAL AND FUNCTIONAL CHANGES IN THE GEMINAL EPITHELIUM IN CHRONIC CATARRHAL GINGIVITIS IN CHILDREN

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ABSTRACT

In order to determine the dynamics of morphological and functional parameters of the gingival epithelium in chronic catarrhal gingivitis in children under the influence of drug correction, 60 children aged 12-17 years (35 boys and 25 girls) were examined.

Periodontal tissue disease is one of the diseases known to mankind since ancient times. With the progress of civilization, the prevalence of inflammatory periodontal diseases has increased dramatically. In the 30s-50s of our century, this pathology was the lot of people aged 40 years and older. Over the past 15-20 years, inflammatory periodontal diseases, not only in our country, but throughout the world, have become much younger [9]. This was established in the course of epidemiological surveys of the population, the methodology of which provides for the purposeful determination of indicators characterizing the state of periodontal tissues [1,2,7]. Systemic diseases, of course, affect the condition of the periodontium, but this effect aggravates the course of an already existing process, may increase the risk of its occurrence, but are not the direct cause of the disease [5]. The frequent combination of gingivitis, periodontitis with diseases of the upper digestive tract indicates the regularity of this relationship and the

universality of the mechanisms of their development [4,9]. An analysis of the literature found that microcirculation disorder occupies one of the leading places in the pathogenesis of inflammatory and degenerative periodontal diseases [6,8,9]. The projective and therapeutic effect of L-arginine on periodontal tissues and gastric mucosa has been experimentally proven. The author substantiates the need for further study of the protective role of L-arginine in dentistry and gastroenterology in joint forms of pathological processes in periodontal tissues and parts of the digestive system [3,4,7]. The purpose of the study was to determine the dynamics of morphological and functional parameters of the gingival epithelium in chronic catarrhal gingivitis in children under the influence of drug correction. Material and research methods. The study involved 60 children aged 12-17 years (35 boys and 25 girls), united in 3 groups. The first group included 14 somatically healthy children with clinically healthy periodontium. The second

group included 25 somatically healthy children with chronic generalized catarrhal gingivitis. The third group included 21 children with chronic generalized catarrhal gingivitis against the background of chronic gastritis and duodenitis with a disease duration of more than two years. The contingent of children with chronic catarrhal gingivitis was recruited from patients of the regional children's clinical hospital who underwent research and treatment in the gastroenterological department. Diagnosis of the pathology of the gastroduodenal zone was carried out in accordance with the Protocols for the diagnosis and treatment of gastroenterological diseases in children (Standards for the diagnosis and treatment of pediatric gastroenterology for RChMMC. Ministry of Health of Uzbekistan. Tashkent. 07/04/2013). When making a dental diagnosis, the classification of periodontal diseases adopted at the 16th Plenum of the All-Union Scientific Society of Dentists (1983) was used. For cytological examination, impressions were taken from the gums in the area of the frontal and chewing teeth (6 impressions for each child) using a target: a sterile wedge-shaped fragment of an eraser with a narrow part of no more than 1 mm. By lightly pressing the target against the area under study, the material was taken and transferred in the form of imprints onto a glass slide. The smears were fixed and stained according to the Romanovsky-Giemsa method. In 10 fields of view, the absolute and percentage content of epithelial (basal; nucleated cells of the spiny layer; keratinized cells lacking nuclei) and connective tissue cells were counted: polymorphonuclear leukocytes (PMNL), intact monocytes, naked monocytes. The number of epithelial cells

with signs of cytopathology was determined: dystrophic altered cells with vacuolated cytoplasm, with a deformed nucleus; cells contaminated with microorganisms [3]. Determination of the adhesive properties of microorganisms *C. albicans* strain: CCM 885 ATCC10231 = 300001 was carried out by the express method of V.I. Brillis, (1986) on the model "gingival epithelium - *C. albicans*" [1]. Gingival epithelial cells were obtained by scraping with a dry sterile spatula from the surface of the gums of the upper and lower jaws, after which the spatula was placed in a sterile container with 2 ml of 0.15 M phosphate-buffered saline (pH = 7.2). Scrapings were taken in the morning before eating and brushing teeth. The degree of adhesiveness of the strain was judged by the following indicators:

- average adhesion index (AAI)
- the average number of microorganisms attached to the epitheliocyte;
- coefficient of participation of epitheliocytes in the adhesive process (Cpe)
- the percentage of epitheliocytes that have adherent microorganisms on their surface;

CPE from 0 to 1.0 corresponds to zero adhesiveness, from 1.01 to 2.0 - low, from 2.01 to 4 - medium, more than 4 - high adhesiveness. In all groups of children, classes were held to teach oral hygiene. In the second group, children received drug complex No. 1, consisting of quercetin (granules), Calcium-D3 Nycomed (tablets) and 0.25% Derinat solution. Derinat was used in the form of applications. The gauze swabs were moistened with the preparation and applied to the gums of the upper and lower jaws for 10-15 minutes. twice a day after brushing your teeth. In the third group, the drug complex No. 2 consisted of altana (tablets), citrarginine (solution for oral

administration) and 0.25% solution of Derinat (for applications). Treatment complexes were used for a month according to the manufacturer's instructions. Treatment of gastroduodenal pathology in the third group of children was carried out in accordance with the Protocols for the diagnosis and treatment of gastroenterological diseases in children (Standards for the diagnosis and treatment of pediatric gastroenterology for RChMMC. Ministry of Health of Uzbekistan. Tashkent. 04.07.2013). Statistical processing of data from clinical and cytological studies was carried out with using the STATISTICA 6.1 licensed program. The frequency of signs, the arithmetic mean (M), the error of the mean (m), Student's test of significance (t), and the degree of significance of differences (p) were determined. Research results and their discussion The initial results of the analysis of cellular elements in the imprints of the gingival epithelium showed that in children with chronic catarrhal gingivitis there is a shift towards less mature cellular forms, it is most significant in children with concomitant chronic gastritis and duodenitis (Group 3). Consequently, proliferative processes predominate in the gingival epithelium in chronic generalized catarrhal gingivitis. The high level of proliferation is due not only to its direct stimulation, but also to the inclusion of negative feedback mechanisms. This implies that accelerated cell death leads to increased neoplasm. In the third group, proliferative processes are the most intense, since with concomitant gastroduodenal pathology in the gum, the area of active capillaries decreases, and epithelial trophism worsens [9]. Thus, the process of adaptation to chronic hypoxia begins with the activation of mechanisms

that are of emergency importance - the intensification of proliferative processes, then those mechanisms that determine increased resistance to hypoxia are turned on. Such shifts are of an adaptive nature and are aimed at maintaining homeostasis. At the same time, in children with chronic catarrhal gingivitis, the number of cells with cytopathological phenomena significantly increases, most pronounced in children with concomitant gastroduodenal pathology. It can be said that compensatory processes are not effective enough, since there is no full-fledged cell differentiation, the number of immature cell forms and cells with cytopathological phenomena increases in the epithelium. Violation of the morphology of the epithelial layer cannot but affect the usefulness of its functions. In the "gingival epithelium - *C. albicans*" system, the adhesive ability of the epithelium to pathogenic microorganisms in children with chronic catarrhal gingivitis is growing. It is known that *C. albicans* actively co-adheres with pathogenic streptococci [5], which cause periodontal disease; therefore, a violation of the functional properties of epitheliocytes leads to a deterioration in the hygienic state of the oral cavity. In children of the 2nd and 3rd groups, the percentage of epitheliocytes with adherent microorganisms on their surface increased by 2.07 and 3.42 times, and the average number of microorganisms attached to one epithelial cell increased by 1.33 and 2.02 times, respectively, in comparison with the control group (Rice. one). Analysis of the imprints of the gingival epithelium, carried out after the course of treatment, showed an increase in the percentage of cells of the terminal stages of differentiation in both groups of children, which indicates that the rate of proliferation

processes is approaching that of the control group.

Fig.1. Indicators of adhesive properties of gingival epitheliocytes in children

The percentage of cells with cytopathological phenomena in the second and third groups of children significantly decreased: with vacuolized cytoplasm (in 1.96 and 1.74), with a deformed nucleus (in 1.62 and 1.27), contaminated with microorganisms (in 2.42 and 1.92 times), respectively. Significantly decreased, although not returned to normal, the percentage of PMAL. There were multidirectional unreliable changes in the content of intact monocytes: in the second group, the number of cells increased slightly, and in the third group, it decreased. The content of bare-nuclear monocytes approached the norm in the second group of subjects, in the third group it was close to the norm, both before and after treatment. After the treatment, there were positive changes in the functional properties of gingival epitheliocytes in children with chronic catarrhal gingivitis. The number of epitheliocytes with adherent microorganisms on their surface significantly decreased both in the second

and third groups of children (by 1.69 and 2.10 times, respectively).

The average number of microorganisms attached to the epitheliocyte tended to decrease in somatically healthy children with chronic catarrhal gingivitis and decreased by 1.59 times in children with background gastroduodenal pathology. Findings. After the implementation of therapeutic measures aimed at improving the trophism of the gingival epithelial layer in children with chronic catarrhal gingivitis, the following changes occurred in the cytological picture of imprints from the gums: the percentage of cells of the terminal stages of differentiation increased, the percentage of cells with cytopathological phenomena decreased. Significantly decreased, although not returned to normal, the percentage of PMAL. The percentage of epithelial cells with adherent microorganisms decreased. The treatment was more effective in the group of somatically healthy children with chronic

catarrhal gingivitis. The improvement in cellular homeostasis after the treatment of periodontal diseases is explained by a decrease in the activity of the inflammatory process in the gums in patients of the second group, an improvement in the trophism of periodontal tissues in patients of the third group against the background of remission of gastroduodenal pathology. The treatment contributed to the improvement of the cytogram parameters, however, there

was no complete recovery of all cytological parameters in patients. For a stable improvement in cellular parameters, repeated courses of therapeutic measures are required (2-3 times a year).

In the future, it is planned to study the morphological and functional parameters of the gingival epithelium in children with various clinical and morphological forms of gastritis and duodenitis.

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